

Research Article

Eco Composite Films from Pumpkin By-Products

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Abstract: *The increasing concern over plastic pollution has driven the development of biodegradable alternative using natural and renewable resources. Pumpkin waste was processed into a film forming solution and combined with natural polymers to enhance the flexibility and strength. The aims of this study to produce eco-composite films from pumpkin by-products such as peels and seeds by utilizing their natural polymers such as cellulose, pectin and proteins. The films were prepared with peels and seeds and treated with acetic acid, glycerine, gelatine and cornstarch to enhance their chemical and mechanical properties. The findings show that within 8 days, both peels sample and mixed sample fully degraded while seeds sample partially degraded. For the swelling test, water revealed the highest swelling in the mixed sample. Next for the solubility test, the findings demonstrated that all the sample are soluble in ammonia NH₃ and sulphuric acid H₂SO₄ yet insoluble in water, acetone and ethyl alcohol. Lastly, for tensile stress test, it shows that mixed sample had the highest strength compared to peels sample and seeds sample.*

Keywords: Pumpkin waste; Biodegradability test; Swelling test; Solubility test; Tensile Strength test.

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1. INTRODUCTION

These days, the world is filled with plastics as everyone is using plastics in their daily life. Plastics are useful for people but also, gives us problems. One of the problems that we can obviously see the plastics are thrown anywhere, not just at the road site but also in the ocean. This issue gives impact towards the environment including a danger threat to the other living. As people know, plastics are hard to decompose. It takes years for it to fully decompose. This is why people start to make biodegradable plastics so that the plastic we used can be decompose easily. Bioplastic is the type of plastic material that was made from renewable materials that can be bio-based or biodegradable or both. Some of the plastics can be bio-based but not biodegradable and some of it can be biodegradable but not bio-based.

A plant like pumpkin is full of benefits. Pumpkin is rich with their content of natural polymers such as pectin, cellulose, and proteins. The peels of the pumpkin contain phenolic compounds, carotenoids, and tocopherols while the seeds are rich in minerals such as magnesium, zinc, iron, calcium, and phosphorus (Lalnunthari et al., 2019). Because of these characteristics, pumpkin is the suitable plant to form

a film with a good biodegradability, flexibility, and strong mechanical. This conversion also will produce a film that can be naturally dissolves in soil or water, encouraging the development of sustainable materials. By creating biodegradable plastic films from pumpkin seeds and peels and evaluating their swelling, solubility, biodegradability, and tensile stress this research seeks to address these issues. The film composition must be improved to obtain desired structural and barrier properties while maintaining environment sustainability. In addition to help to value waste, this strategy encourages the creation of affordable biodegradable plastic as a substitute that can lessen the dependency on petrochemical plastics.

2. OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of this study is to develop biodegradable films using pumpkin seeds and peels as raw materials, utilizing their natural polymers. Additionally, the study aims to evaluate the physical properties of the produced bioplastic films, with a particular focus on biodegradability, solubility, swelling behavior, and tensile strength, in order to determine which sample exhibits the most optimal performance characteristics.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past few years, the extensive consumption of synthetic, non-renewable plastics that are made from petroleum has produced garbage that brings a threat to the environment. According to official statistics, the world's plastic manufacturing has grown significantly since the 1950s, averaging 8% annually (Gao et al., 2023).

3.1 *Polymers Science Theory*

According to Huang et al. (2025), natural polymers being derived from renewable resources that are biodegradable and environmentally friendly. Natural polymers like proteins, cellulose and starch may reduce the reliance on fossil fuels and greenhouse gas emissions. Example of the applications of natural polymers due to their biocompatibility and biodegradability are food packaging biodegradable films and medical devices. On the other hand, natural polymers frequently have issues with poor mechanical strength and low water vapor resistance which restricts their application in processes requiring a lot of heat and pressure. In contrast, synthetic polymers are known for their durability and versatility that making them suitable for a wide range of applications. The example of synthetic polymers are polyethylene and polyvinyl alcohol.

Nilsson et al. (2025) reported that, natural polymers often decompose more quickly and have a lower toxicity. For the application of natural polymers, they can be chemically modified to improve qualities like water resistance and mechanical strength, which makes them appropriate for particular uses. Natural and synthetic polymers are important in many industries. Natural polymers come from renewable sources that are biodegradable. Synthetic polymers, made from petrochemicals that are durable and versatile. Understanding the differences between them is key to creating sustainable materials.

3.2 *Biodegradation Mechanism*

For microbial degradation, most microorganisms play the main role. Many soil-dwelling bacteria such as *Pseudomonas* sp., *Streptococcus* sp., *Staphylococcus* sp., *Bacillus* sp., and *Moraxella* sp., may help in the biodegradation of bioplastics. These microbes aid in the breaking down of polymer chains especially

in polymers made of starch. Environmental factors such as temperature, pH, and moisture content impact the biodegradation process. Specifically, water aids microbial activity, which hastens the digestion of bioplastics. Chemicals such as glycerol can increase the ability of the material to take up water which can stimulate the rapid breakdown of the material (Shubham Bhausahab, 2023).

Nilsson et al. (2025) reported that one of the most important things that influence how fast polymers degrade is temperature. Typically, the greater the temperature, the quicker chemical reactions take place, which makes materials degrade quicker. Melting point and crystallinity are temperature-dependent properties that affect material stability and can be ascertained by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Next, water can catalyse the degradation of polymers, particularly polymers that are intended to degrade biologically. In order to determine the stability and performance of polymers, methods like spectroscopy and chromatography are used to examine their solubility and degradation under exposure to water. Other than that, the pH of the environment also can change the chemical stability of a polymer. The material can deteriorate through hydrolysis or other chemical processes triggered by pH change. To gather credible data on the degradation of polymers, it is important to monitor and report pH values when testing.

3.3 Environmental Science Concepts

Biodegradable polymers are made to break down naturally in the environment by biological processes into non-toxic substances like water and carbon dioxide. By using biodegradable plastics, it may decrease the environmental impact of plastic waste and may promote to the ecological balance. However, the challenges for it were technical and economic challenges. The cost of producing water-soluble and biodegradable polymers can be higher than that for conventional plastics, which limits their widespread use. It is because to match the performance (strength, durability, flexibility) of conventional plastics, biodegradable polymers often need additives or blending, which increases the cost. In other words, they need technological advancements in an attempt to reduce the cost of production and improve the mechanical properties of such materials (Huang et al., 2025). For the life cycle analysis, unlike conventional plastics, biodegradable polymers such as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) break down in normal environmental conditions to minimize long-term environmental contamination. Bioplastics made from sustainable resources, such as orange peel, provide a green solution in decreasing greenhouse gas emissions and fossil fuel dependence (Huang et al., 2025). According to Nilsson et al. (2025), water-soluble plastics are not yet completely regulated, indicating a gap in environmental protection policies despite the European Union's implementation of regulations to control the use of microplastics. More life cycle analysis is required to inform regulatory choices due to the potential for bioaccumulation and long-term environmental consequences of non-biodegradable water-soluble polymers.

3.4 Seeds and Peels for Biodegradable Film

According to Lalnunthari et al. (2019), the components of pumpkin seeds are pectin and protein. Pectin is a polysaccharide that can be utilised in film formation. It is because pectin has gelling properties that make it suitable for creating biodegradable films. Since pumpkin contains a protein component, it can improve the mechanical properties of the films when it is combined with pectin. For example, the tensile strength and flexibility of films. Next, for the pumpkin peels, it contained fibre and antioxidants. Pumpkins are rich in fibres, which can contribute to the structural integrity of biodegradable films. It may provide a more robust barrier against moisture. Since natural fibres decompose faster in the environment than synthetic materials, using pumpkin peel fibres in film formulations can also increase the final product's biodegradability. Phenolic substances with antioxidant qualities can be found in pumpkin peels. These compounds can enhance the functional characteristics of biodegradable films, potentially increasing their

shelf life and stability. The antioxidant activity of these compounds may also contribute to the overall health benefits, making them more appealing to consumers.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Preparation of Pumpkin Paste from Pumpkin Peels

Pumpkin peels were cut into pieces as thin as we could and were boiled in water for 30 minutes. After 30 minutes, the water was decanted, and the peels were left dried on filter paper. After drying, the peels were grinded using the mortar until the peels turn into a paste.

4.2 Preparation of Pumpkin Powder from Pumpkin Seeds

Pumpkin seeds were separated from the pumpkin filling and washed using the water. After washing, we dried the seeds using oven for 20 minutes at temperature 130°C. After the seeds dried, we blended it using blender until it formed into powder.

4.3 Production of the Polymer

There are three samples which are peels sample, seeds sample, and mixed sample. The production of polymer was conducted by adding 50 mL distilled water and 3g of cornstarch into a beaker. The mixture was stirred on the hot plate until it reaches a gel texture and reached 50°C. After that, 7g of gelatin were added into the mixture. The mixture was stirred until it evenly mixed and reached 70°C. 1 mL of acetic acid was added afterwards and mixed. After the process, the sample was put into the mixture and mix it well while the mixture still in high temperature. This process repeated for the three of sample with the mass of 10g of peels paste, 5g of seeds powder and 5g of peels paste combined with 5g of seeds powder. The samples were poured into the aluminium trays and was dried using air dry for 2-3 days.

4.4 Biodegradability Test

Solubility test is conducted to see if the samples's polymers can be breakdown easily by the microorganisms and how long it takes to breakdown the polymer of the samples. The three samples were cut into the same size and buried in beakers containing soil for 8 days. Small amount of water was spattered on top of the soil to maintain the moisture of the soil for microorganisms' activities in breaking down the chemical bonds.

4.5 Swelling Test

Swelling test is conducted to see how well the three different samples absorbs the chemical and expands. The weigh of the samples before doing the test were taken to compare with the aftermath of the test. This test is carried out by 3 types of solvent which are water, methanol and chloroform. The samples that already weighed were put into the beaker and left untouched. After few hours, the sample's weigh was taken.

4.6 Solubility Test

The test conducted to observe which of the three samples easy to dissolve into the solvents. The samples were cut into small pieces and put into the test tube. Each of the test tube contains one type of solvent which are water, ammonia, acetone, ethyl alcohol and acetic sulphuric acid.

4.7 Tensile Stress Test

Tensile stress test conducted on the sample to measure how much weight that the three of the samples can handle before it breaks. The samples were measured and cut into medium size pieces. After that, the samples were attached to the spring balance on one of the end of the sample and the other side was attached with the weight started from 50g. The amount of weight will be added more until the samples finally breaks.

5. DATA/RESULTS

5.1 Biodegradation Test

Table 1. Result of Biodegradability Test for a period of 8 days in the soil

Sample	Observation		
	Day 1	Day 4	Day 8
Peels	Shiny and firm	Breaking into smaller pieces	Fully degraded
Seeds	Shiny and firm	Softer	Partially degraded, Black
Mixed	Shiny and firm	Breaking into smaller pieces	Fully degraded

Swelling Test

Figure 1. A graph of Differences Swelling Test in different solvents.

5.2 Solubility Test

Table 2. Result of Solubility Test in different solvents

Sample	Solvents				
	Ammonia	Acetone	Water	Ethyl alcohol	Sulphuric acid
Peels	+	-	-	-	+, become black
Seeds	+	-	-	-	+, become black
Mixed	+	-	-	-	+, become black

+ = Positive , - = Negative

5.3 Tensile Stress Test

Table 3. Result of Tensile Stress Test

Sample	Tensile Stress (N/m ²)
Peels	11
Seeds	11
Mixed	13

6. DISCUSSION/ANALYSIS

6.1 Biodegradation Test

In biology, degradation refers to the process of breaking down of complex materials into simpler components. This process can occur through various mechanisms including chemicals, physicals or biological means. Biodegradation primarily involves in the breakdown of organic compounds by living organisms, specifically microorganisms. For instance, fungi and bacteria (Patel et al., 2022). Both removal of pollutants from the environment and recycling nutrient in ecosystems are depends on this process (Aboudi et al., 2021). On day 1, all the samples which are peels, seeds and mixed appeared shiny and firm. It indicating that the samples were fresh and structurally intact the start of the observation period. By day 4, peels sample and mixed sample start to be breaking into smaller pieces that indicate the onset of degradation. This implies that, the materials are more vulnerable to the microbial breakdown compared to seed. However, by day 4, the seeds only become softer. This observation showing slower degradation because of their tougher outer coat, which may lead to resistance decomposition (Patel et al., 2022). After 8 days of being left, both peels sample and mixed sample were fully degraded. The degradation rate of peel sample and mixed sample were similar. It may be because in the mixed sample it has peels as the primary degradable component. On the other hand, the seeds sample showed only partially degraded and become black. It is showing that although internal or on the surface decomposition had started, complete breakdown process had not yet occurred. The sample become black, it may potentially indicate the beginning of degradation in the seed coat or because of fungal and microbial activity (Aboudi et al., 2021). Overall, the result shows that the peels sample degrade faster than seed. This result aligns with the common composting knowledge, where woody component often degrades more slowly due to the high lignin

component on the seeds. The complex organic polymer lignin gives materials strength and decay resistance (Patel et al., 2022).

6.2 Swelling Test

Swelling test is a test where we observe how much the samples absorb the solvents and expand without dissolving in the solvents after being left for two hours. This test reflects on each of the samples' polarity and the interaction of the solvent with the samples' structure. Based on our results, each of the samples got higher mass after being dissolved in water while in methanol and chloroform, the results show that the mass after dissolved is lower compared to water. This shows that three of the samples have a high swelling rate in water and a low swelling rate in methanol and chloroform. The peel sample is rich with fibres, cellulose and lignin which are highly polar and rigid polymers. They form strong hydrogen bonds, making the structure tightly bonded. This results in a high absorbance rate in water but resists swelling in methanol and chloroform (Hussain et al., 2022). Next, the seed sample contains more proteins and lipids. Protein is polar and contributes to water absorption, while lipids are adding some hydrophobic in the sample, limiting the solvent interaction. This makes the sample have a low swelling rate in less polar and nonpolar solvents such as methanol and chloroform (Hussain et al., 2022). Last one is the mixed sample. The mixed sample combines cellulose, lignin, proteins and lipids. This combination matrix can restrict solvent absorption especially in methanol and chloroform. The sample absorbs water more because of the addition of hydrophilic components in it. The water was absorbed more due to the hydrophilic group in the samples (e.g. starch) which results in higher mass and swelling rate (Zhang et al., 2024). While in methanol, the swelling rate is less than in water. It is because methanol is less polar than water, resulting for the sample to partially absorb the solvent and the chain of the polymer did not interact with methanol (Roy, 2023). While for chloroform, the swelling rate is lesser than in water and methanol because it has a very less interaction with the samples. It cannot absorb the polymer in the samples successfully and might be because chloroform is a non-polar solvent.

6.3 Solubility Test

The purpose of this solubility test is to determine how the sample behaves when exposed to the different solvents like water, ammonia, acetone, sulphuric acid and ethyl alcohol over 30 minutes. The findings show that all the sample (peels, seeds and mixed) is soluble in ammonia NH_3 and sulphuric acid H_2SO_4 . This finding indicated the sample was interacted with polar and strong acid solutions. The possible approaches for the solubility in distilled water have to do with the hydrophilic nature of the starches and proteins that might be found in pumpkin by-product (Patel et al., 2022). Next, the sample turned dark after being placed in the H_2SO_4 solution. Concentrated sulphuric acid is a strong dehydrating and oxidizing agent, which can cause oxidation reactions and carbonization of the polymer or organic matter which results in turning the sample black (Lee et al., 2022). In contrast, all the sample showed insoluble in water, acetone and ethyl alcohol. The sample has potential resistance in ketone-containing environments (Patel et al., 2022). All in all, there is no difference of solubility between all the sample (peels, seeds and mixed) as all the samples reacted similarly to each solvent. The sample indicates selective solubility, being vulnerable to polar and acidic conditions but resistant to organic solvents. When analysing these samples for biodegradable applications, this feature should be considered, particularly in situations where solvent exposure is expected.

6.4 Tensile Stress Test

Tensile stress test is a test where we measure the maximum weight or force that the three of the samples can handle before it finally breaks (Michigan Technological University, 2019). This test also shows how strong and flexible the performance of the samples to be used for daily life. To calculate the tensile strength of the samples, we used the formula $\sigma = F/A$. From the results we got, we found out that the sample 3 which is the mixed sample has higher tensile strength compared to peels sample and seeds sample. The tensile strength for mixed sample is 13 N/m² while for peels sample and seeds sample, the tensile strength is 11 N/m² respectively. This shows that the mixed samples are better than the not mixed samples because the mixed sample can withstand more force as they were made with combined different type of fibers (Yashas Gowda et al., 2018). The higher the stress tolerance, the stronger the sample. In addition, this mixed fiber creates a tighter connected structure which resulting to stronger bonding between the molecules. The stronger bonding is the reason why the mixed sample is tougher and not easily to break compared to the peels sample and seeds sample.

7. CONCLUSION

The biodegradable films were successfully developed by using the pumpkin peels and seeds. Their polymers play the crucial roles in forming the films. Other than that, we managed to evaluate each of the samples physical and chemical properties through four types of tests. The results of the tests already taken. Last but not least, our pumpkin-based biofilms show better performance in strength especially our mixed sample compared to peels sample and seeds sample and it is faster in degradation than the conventional plastic. This can reduce the impact on the environment and supporting the waste reduction efforts. From this research also, we can conclude that sample mixed is better in performance compared to peel only sample and seed only sample.

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